

A Case of Infant Malignant Lymphoma that Healed Completely after Oral Administrations of 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde

Case Report

Okazaki K*

Okazaki Medical Clinic, Ukyoku, Kyoto Japan.

In 1985, Mutsuyuki Kochi [1, 2] reported a novel anti-tumor agent after acquiring a Japanese Patent in 1969. According to his patent, 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde is an anti-tumor agent without any side-effects. My impression is that this stuff is capable of preventing carcinogenesis when used quantitatively sufficiently. In order to treat developed cancers, you ought to start giving your cancer patient a small dose of the stuff because, otherwise, the patient may suffer from a serious hemorrhage of the tumor caused by excessive necroses. Therefore, lymphomas and leukemias can be treated more easily because these tumors have no blood vessels. Consequently, those who have these diseases can receive considerably large dose of the stuff.

A 2-year-old girl (R.I.) was diagnosed to have a cervical malignant lymphoma with diameter of 50mm at a local Cancer Center on

November 1, 2012. Her parent demanded me to prescribe her with 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde on November 12, 2012. I prescribed daily 333mg of 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde as an aqueous solution of 500mg % for her on November 16, 2012. I raised the doses to daily 500mg in February, 2013, in early summer of 2013, the tumor disappeared. As of September 27, 2017, she is enjoying a healthy life.

References

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- [2]. Kochi M. Manufacturing Process of Anticancer Substance. Japanese Patent, No.560349; 1969.

*Corresponding Author:

Kimihiko Okazaki,
Okazaki Medical Clinic, Ukyoku, Kyoto, Japan.
E-mail: ma13081x@ma1.seikyou.ne.jp

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